

Moderating Effect of Technology on Users' Attributes and E-Government Information System Success in Tanzania

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ABSTRACT

Informed by Information System (IS) success model, most studies overlook users' attributes and do not consider the effect of technology in IS success area. The main aim of this paper was to analyze the moderating effect of technology on the relationship between users' attributes and IS success for e-government implementation in Tanzania. Quantitative method was utilized to test the hypothesis for the moderation effect. The area is Dar es Salaam in Tanzania. A survey was made to tax practitioners from the Tanzania Revenue Authority by use of a self administered questionnaire. Data collected from 246 respondents was analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) assisted with SmartPLS 3. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between users' attributes and IS success ($p = 0.000$). Further results showed that technology does moderate the relationship between users' attributes and IS success ($p = 0.001$).

Keyword: technology, users' attributes, information system success

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Advancement in technology and use of IS offers incredible opportunities to activities related to information and communication technology (ICT) and in particular, electronic government (e-government). E-government as a vital instrument to governments, it improves efficiency and effectiveness in performing activities (Kalu and Masri, 2019; Sarrayrih and Sriram, 2015). It has potential in developing government systems for public activities in any country (Fakhruzzaman, 2019). Public activities which are operated through e-government, include e-payment, which refers to electronic payment where citizens pay their bills and many other financial transactions by use of electronic instruments like mobile money and telegraphic transfers; as well as e-assessment, which stands for electronic assessment in which activities involving assessment such as assessing taxes and work performance are made electronically (Khadaroo, Wong and Abdullah, 2013). Ability to use electronic services that can be stimulated by sound users' attributes (such as ICT skills) seems important for IS success (Zhang, Wang and Duan, 2016). Studies conducted in the area of IS for e-government relate its success with users' attitude, services quality issues and the like; however, little is known on the influence of users attributes to IS success for e-government as well as the effect of technology on this relationship.

The meaning of IS success is not homogeneous across different settings (DeLone and McLean, 2016). Proposed measures of IS success include process reforms; user satisfaction; system quality; information quality; service quality together with economic returns; others include task characteristics; user characteristics; social characteristics; project characteristics (structure); use, intention usage, satisfaction and net benefits (for instance cost reduction, saving time and enhanced transparency) which may be derived on usage (Peter, Delone and McLean, 2013; Alomari, Woods and Sandhu, 2012; DeLone and McLean, 2003). IS success is associated further with the technology appropriateness (Al-Shboul *et al.*, 2014). DeLone and McLean (2016) argue that researchers who use to evaluate IS success in e-government development and data transmission, do so by applying technological aspects.

Technology for IS success encompass the internal and external technologies relevant to the organization. They cover Information Technology (IT) standard, technical expertise, compatibility, trust and security of data, system fit, network as well as ICT infrastructure (Makau, Omwenga and Muranga, 2015; Bwalya and Mutula, 2015; Wu, 2014; Rokhman, 2011; Al-Rahbi, Al-Harrasi and Al-Wahaibi, 2012). Technologies may include both equipment as well as processes (Tornatzky and Fleisher, 1990); however, the costs of acquiring and positioning of technology seem to be high and hinders smooth e-government operations, mostly in developing countries like Tanzania. In addition, consideration of technology related matters will not have positive impact without taking into account users applying the developed systems.

It is argued that users considerations like acceptance of the developed technologies and systems as well as their attributes (such as age, experience, gender and knowledge) seem to be imperative for e-government (Fakhoury and Aubert, 2017; Sarrayrih and Sriram, 2015; Oseni, Dingley and Hart, 2015). For instance, Oseni *et al.* (2015) point the relevance of users who have to adopt the system for usage – ultimately deriving benefits from the government electronic services (interpreted as IS success in e-government). Information systems, therefore, are expected to constitute a form of technology that can assist citizens in managing resources and data related to specific government activity (Fakhruzzaman, 2019). Nevertheless, there exists hindrance on usage as most developing countries' citizens including Tanzanians are not able to access broadband and most e-government projects fail (Kanaan, Hassan and Shahzad, 2016; United Republic of Tanzania, 2016).

In addition, Ishengoma, Mselle and Mongi (2018) pointed several ICT problems including citizens' difficulties in usability and access. The low usage level can be attributed to how users understand ICT matters; and lack of awareness to the benefits which ICT provides (Olaolu *et al.*, 2018). Besides, Lupilya and Jung (2015) observed outdated telecommunications and ICT policies hindering smooth running of the electronic services. Due to such challenges it was imperative to

study about IS success in Tanzania, to enable evaluation of concerns about users' attributes (such as education and age) relevant for e-government. Conceptually, the study assessed the moderating effect of technology on the relationship between users' attributes and IS success for e-government. Accordingly, the findings provide further knowledge on IS success area for proper e-government implementation to different stakeholders including public administrators and academicians.

The organization of this paper is as follows: firstly, theoretical (basing on the IS success model), empirical and conceptual frameworks are presented. Thereafter, a methodology on how this research was conducted is outlined. Study findings are then discussed. Subsequently, the paper provides conclusions and recommendations on the observed findings. Finally, outline of limitations and areas for future research presented.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The manner in which the success of an information system is evaluated change over time due to different IT purposes, context and impact (DeLone and McLean, 2016). IS success research evaluates the effective design, distribution and use of information by applying technology. Zhang *et al.* (2016) stress on the role of users attributes (human actors) for IS success as through it, users can be able to use the systems. This study is informed by IS success model which has six interrelated variables. The variables are: system quality, service quality, information quality, use or intention to use the system, user satisfaction and net benefits. DeLone and McLean (2003) developed a model to address proposed arguments emerged from some criticisms on their original model of 1992 (Seddon, 1997). Original authors of the 1992 IS success model came up with an updated IS success model taking into account an additional variable, service quality. Likewise, a new model combined IS impact measures and termed them as net benefits. Net benefits' construct was taken to represent end point IS success measure because it would mean both positive and negative outcomes that could occur.

Another feature in the new model is the inclusion of intention to use the system; measuring attitude of users in relation to the IS success. This study applied "intention to use" variable because it could not be relevant to use variable "use" due to existence of the mandatory systems in Tanzania public institutions. Use construct was retained in the updated model. Formerly, use variable was questioned by Seddon (1997). It was not clear whether IS use implies benefits from use; future IS use; or an event in a process of learning IS. However, DeLone and McLean (2003) agreed to retain usage because "use" was observed to continue to be a criterion variable in many reviewed empirical works, since without use, one cannot know the IS benefits.

The DeLone and McLean (2003) IS success model has been widely used by various authors in different contexts. Wong (2011) proposed a revision of the model by adding an item, adaptability to eternal needs to meet customers' specifications (appropriate technology); Seen, Rouse and Beaumont (2007) combined its variables with other models and stress on technology innovativeness for IS success. Likewise, an item appropriate technology appeared vital to this study and it was reflected in technology variable which moderates the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. Furthermore, this study mapped the IS success model variable "net benefits" into different measures including, cost reduction, enhanced transparency and efficiency (faster decision making). The net benefits' measures and intention to use the systems were grouped in the IS success construct which represents a study's dependent variable. In addition, to suit current users' experience in public electronic services, a study combined users' attributes (such as age, ICT knowledge and age) with the variables found in the DeLone and McLean (2003) IS success model. Other technology appropriateness matters are reflected in the IS quality issues.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Most studies analyzing e-government success use variables commented by the IS success models while overlooking issues related to users. Tanzania as one of the developing countries experiences

ICT problems concerning users (ICT know how and the like) and technology itself (ICT infrastructure and so forth). The ICT problems include: unreliable technology (Lupilya and Jung, 2015); usability issues (Ishengoma *et al.*, 2018); knowledge and internet language to users pointed in the 2016 National ICT Policy; funding to facilitate these ICT needs (Nabafu and Maiga, 2012); and sometimes users are unable to access the developed e-government projects (United Republic of Tanzania, 2016; Kanaan *et al.*, 2016); which can be associated with poor ICT knowledge (Olaolu *et al.*, 2018). Hence, it is imperative to review users' traits and technology for IS success in e-government success as some of the identified problems can be covered by sound users' attributes including education, experience and ICT skills.

Users non-biographic attributes (experience, ICT skills) and biographic characteristics (such as age and gender) are considered vital for IS success in different ways (Al-Athmay, 2013, Wittendorp, 2017; Rahman *et al.*, 2014). Users possessing ICT skills use easily e-government services (Wittendorp, 2017). Knowledge about e-government services especially during initial learning experience is useful for IS success as it improves usage habits (Fakhoury and Aubert, 2017). In other hand, Chopra and Rajan (2016) show experience as a moderating variable. In examining the differences of taxpayers' attitude to use e-government in form of e-filing among gender, level of education, experience and learning of the e-filing system in Malaysia ; it was observed by Ilias, Mohd and Mohd (2009) that users' traits of gender and age show different impact in IS success for e-government implementation. The study found that other non-biographic factors like experience to be relevant in IS success; however, gender provides no differences in terms of users' attitude in the established e-government system.

Yet, Al-Shafi and Weerakkody (2010) pointed out that adopters of e-government differ significantly in terms of all traits of gender and age. Gender moderates the influence of the determinants on behavioral intention on e-government such as perceived usefulness; moreover, male use computers more than female, suggesting, gender as an important variable in e-government adoption for successful implementation. Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) propose users attributes of age, gender and experience as moderators of relationships found in IS studies (social influence, facilitating conditions, performance expectancy as compared to intention usage of the systems).

Additionally, Chopra and Rajan (2016) found positive moderating effect of age on the relationship examined between the IS variables and the IS success (that is, IS satisfaction). Conversely, while Hamner and Al-Qahtani (2009) observed a negative effect of age, Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) found evidence that explains a positive effect of age on the behavioral intention and usage of technology for the success of electronic projects. The younger as well as middle age groups are expected to be adopters, while the older age group is expected to be of non-adopters of systems in e-government.

Different findings on users' attributes have been observed in the IS success studies. For instance, while most studies indicate the importance of experience, Albeshier (2015) found that education level and experience have no significant impact in e-government. Moreover, Al-Gahtani *et al.* (2007) found experience to have a negative effect on users' effort expectancy and behavioral intention to use computer for IS success. Effort expectancy (being facilitated by ones' ICT literacy) shows how easy systems are perceived by users.

Conversely, studies indicate ICT literacy as an important and necessary factor for the users to possess for IS success in e-government (United Republic of Tanzania, 2016; United Nations, 2012; Rorissa and Demissie, 2010). Other observations show that men seem to have higher ICT skills than women; and the ICT skills (being the internet skills or any) are negatively correlated to age of the users (Wittendorp, 2017). To address ICT skills and awareness issues, Rahman *et al.* (2014) recommend governments to be more associated with IS issues by including education, provision of ICT awareness as well as ICT regulations for IS success in public electronic projects. However, Ziemba *et al.* (2013) reveal that use and success of IS for e-government is not solely dependent upon ICT skills; proper attention is suggested to other human factors such as ICT supply. Therefore, this paper considers that the users' non-biographic characteristics of experience and education as

well as their biographic features of age and gender relevant in studying e-government activities. These characteristics (age, gender, experience, ICT skills and education) were mapped into users' attributes. Observed users' attributes may shape users' culture in dealing with government electronic services.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study analyzed the moderating effect of technology on the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. The independent variable is users' attributes while the dependent variable is IS success. Technology is the moderator of the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. Therefore this paper has two hypotheses which are:

H₁: Users' attributes is significantly related to IS success.

H₂: Technology moderates the relationship between users' attributes and IS success.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This is a cross-sectional research design and a quantitative method approach was used to analyze the moderating effect of technology on the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. The study area is Dar es Salaam in Tanzania. The unit of analysis was tax practitioners who are users of electronic systems of the Tanzania Revenue Authority. The sampling technique used in this study was convenient sampling in order to obtain information from the practitioners with experience of using electronic services in tax collection. A five point Likert scale self-administered questionnaire from "1 = strongly agree" to "5 = strongly disagree" was used to assess respondents' feedback on their opinions of technology, users' attributes and IS success. The statements used to measure the variables of technology, users' attributes and IS success were adapted from previous studies (Al-Shbouland *et al.*, 2014; Nabafu and Maiga, 2012; Shin, Song and Kang, 2008).

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 below indicates the statements that were used to measure technology, users' attributes and IS success. There were 246 questionnaires returned from the responds and therefore, 246 sample size was quite sufficient for the usage of the analysis tool – of PLS-SEM assisted with SmartPLS 3. Collected data was subjected to reliability and validity test using composite reliability. The composite reliability tests values indicated acceptable values of technology (0.824), users' attribute (0.834) and IS success (0.805). In addition, the developed hypotheses were tested using PLS-SEM. The SPSS Version 20 was also used to provide descriptive statistics of the sampled respondents.

Table 1. Study Variable and Statement Items for Technology

Variable	Variable's item code	Item's description
Technology (TEC)	TEC1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedure manuals are reviewed to comply with ICTs' changes. • Right technologies are being identified.
	TEC2	
	TEC3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems are protected against unauthorized access.
	TEC4	
	TEC5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT infrastructure support e-government implementation. • Users receive assistance from ICT specialists. • Challenges of using websites and government systems hinder the usage of e-
	TEC 6	

		government.
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Table 2. Study Variable and Statement Items for Users’ Attributes

Variable	Variable’s item code	Item’s description
Users’ Attributes (UAT)	UAT1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education level plays an important role in increasing and improving attitude in using online services. • Experienced users on e-services contribute to the implementation of developed electronic government projects as compared to non-experienced. • Older employees have negative attitude to using electronic services. • ICT knowledge stimulates users to do activities electronically. • Young employees are able to learn easily new systems and therefore they can frequently use as compared to older ones. • Females are more likely to prefer doing their work manually as compared to males.
	UAT2	
	UAT3	
	UAT4	
	UAT5	
	UAT6	

Table 3. Study Variable and Statement Items for IS Success

Variable	Variable’s item code	Item’s description
IS Success	ISS1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-government has made ease communication between staff and citizens. • There is reduction of daily working costs. • E-government operations enable faster decision making. • Transparency in government is enhanced. • Electronic operations in government reduce the level of corruption. • Users intend to use e-government if the systems are easy to use.
	ISS2	
	ISS3	
	ISS4	
	ISS5	
	ISS6	

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in Table 4 indicate the characteristic distribution of the respondents whereby majority of them were aged 20 to 30 years (27.6%) and males (58.9%) with post graduate education (43.5%). This suggests that the most of the respondents are young educated males.

Table 4. Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Age	
20-30 years	27.6
31-35 years	17.5
36-40 years	11.4
41-45 years	12.6
46-50 years	11.8

above 50 years	19.1
Gender	
Male	58.9
Female	41.1
Highest Level of Education	
Secondary	2.0
Advanced Secondary	0.8
Diploma	11.4
First Degree	42.3
Post Graduate	43.5

Low outer loadings below the value of 0.70 were dropped. However, the items with acceptable outer loadings of 0.70 and above were retained as shown in Table 5. Values of 0.70 and above indicate item reliability (Hair *et al.*, 2010).

Table 5. Outer Loadings for Technology, User's Attributes and IS Success

	TEC	UAT	ISS
TEC1	0.730		
TEC2	0.898		
TEC3	0.706		
UAT4		0.905	
UAT5		0.782	
ISS1			0.823
ISS6			0.819

The discriminant validity test using the Fornell-Lacker Criterion was done in order to measure degree of differences between constructs. In PLS-SEM, the discriminant validity test measures the degree of differences between the overlapping construct (Hair *et al.*, 2014). Table 6 shows the discriminant validity values which are acceptable due to the AVE being greater than the correlations with other latent constructs. The square root of each construct's Average Variance Extracted (AVE) should have a greater value than the correlations with other latent constructs (Hair *et al.*, 2014).

Table 6. Discriminant Validity for Technology, User's Attributes and IS Success

	ISS	TEC	UAT
ISS	0.821		
TEC	0.323	0.783	
UAT	0.369	0.098	0.846

The collinearity test in Table 7 indicated acceptable Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for TEC1, TEC2, TEC3, UAT4, UAT5, ISS1 and ISS6. Hair *et al.* (2010) and Ringle *et al.* (2015) stated that (VIF) < 4 or (VIF) < 5 is acceptable.

Table 7. Collinearity (VIF) Values for Technology, User's Attributes and IS Success

	VIF
TEC1	1.468
TEC2	1.659
TEC3	1.222
UAT4	1.245

UAT5	1.245
ISS1	1.138
ISS6	1.138

Bootstrapping test was done and the display of path coefficients in terms of T value and P value in Table 8 showed that the relationship between UAT and ISS is significant ($p=0.000$) with T value as 6.617. This implies that users' attributes is significantly related to IS success for e-government implementation. The users' attributes indicators in this study are "young employees are able to learn easily new systems and therefore they can frequently use as compared to older ones" and "females are more likely to prefer doing their work manually as compared to males" which influence IS success indicators being "electronic operations in government reduce the level of corruption" and "users intend to use e-government if the systems are easy to use". The findings of this study differ with the studies by Hamner and Al-Qahtani (2009) and Ilias *et al.* (2009) which found that age and gender had no effect on IS success. The differences in results are because in this study, indicators of users' attributes being age are explained in terms of younger employees' ability to learn than older employees as well as for gender whereby females prefer doing work manually.

Furthermore, technology does moderate the relationship between users' attributes and IS success ($p=0.001$). Although the p-value shows 0.001, this is still an indication that technology is a moderator of the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. The technology indicators that moderate the relationship between users' attributes and IS success are "procedure manuals are reviewed to comply with ICTs' changes", "right technologies are being identified", and "systems are protected against unauthorized access". Previous studies such as Chopra and Rajan (2016) used age a moderator to study IS success whilst this study uses technology as a moderator to contribute literature on IS success for e-government implementation. Additionally, the significant results of this study support the UTAUT theory, and the IS success model by signifying that users' attributes influence IS success for e-government implementation, and that technology as a moderator does have effect on the relationship of users' attributes and IS success for e-government implementation in context of Tanzania.

Table 8. Bootstrapping Test for Technology, User's Attributes and IS Success

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Value
Moderating Effect 1 -> ISS	0.19	0.177	0.056	3.379	0.001
UAT ->ISS	0.325	0.323	0.049	6.617	0.000

5.0 CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this study was to examine the moderating effect of technology on users' attributes and Information System success for e-government implementation. From the findings, this study can conclude that technology significantly moderates the relationship between users' attributes and IS success. Theoretically, the significant results of this study support the application of UTAUT theory and Information System success model in examining moderation effect of technology on the relationship between users' attributes and information systems success for e-government implementation in context of Tanzania. The implication is for government agencies to consider users' attributes such as age and gender that plays an important role in increasing and improving the use of online services in relation to IS success without neglecting technology related matters such as ICT infrastructure. Future research can explore a qualitative approach to understand Information System success for e-government implementation.

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